

STATIC AND FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF CONCRETE SLABS REINFORCED WITH GFRP BARS

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ABSTRACT

Glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) have been employed as internal reinforcement of bridge decks in cold regions, where deicing salts rapidly degrade steel reinforcing bars. Bridge decks should be designed with respect to fatigue loading, which requires the knowledge of the bar and concrete fatigue behavior and of their interaction under cyclic loading. In this paper, the behavior of a GFRP-reinforced concrete slab subjected to a quasi-static 4-point bending test is compared with that of an equal specimen subjected to a fatigue test. These results are also compared with those of pull-out tests of the same bar and concrete.

KEYWORDS

GFRP bars; fatigue; slabs; reinforced concrete; pull-out; bending test.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) bars represent an effective alternative to steel bars to reinforce concrete members exposed to aggressive environments (Carvelli et al., 2010). Among available composite bars, glass FRP (GFRP) bars have been largely employed due to their low cost (compared to other types of composite bar) and high strength and durability (compared to steel bars) (Federation Internationale du Beton, 2007). GFRP bars are particularly attractive as internal reinforcement of bridge decks in cold climates, where the use of deicing salts induces a rapid corrosion of steel reinforcement (Klowak et al., 2006). In this case, the reinforcing bar is subjected to a cyclic loading. Thus, a careful fatigue assessment of the GFRP-reinforced concrete member shall be performed.

The available research on the fatigue behavior of GFRP bars is still limited. Some studies reported results of cyclic tensile tests on bare bars (i.e., not embedded within concrete), whereas in some others the bar was embedded within a concrete block and the tensile load was transferred from the concrete to the bar (Noël & Soudki, 2014). In both cases, fatigue tests up to 4 and 5 million cycles, respectively, were reported in the literature (Adimi et al., 1997; D'Antino et al., 2022). However, contradictory results were reported regarding the effect of the embedding concrete that in some cases was observed to increase the number of fatigue cycles and in some others to increase the bar damage with respect to the case of a corresponding bare bar cyclic test (D'Antino et al., 2022). It should be noted, however, that the gripping system adopted for the bare bar test had a strong influence on the specimen fatigue behavior. Premature failure of bars close to the gripped portion was responsible for the limited fatigue life reported in (Januš et al., 2019). In fact, proper gripping of bare bars allowed for attaining 5 million cycles with no degradation of the bar, as reported in (D'Antino et al., 2022).

The load range, i.e., mean fatigue load and load amplitude, played a fundamental role in determining the bar fatigue life. The European standard ISO 10406-1 (European Committee for Standardization, 2015) requires fatigue tests of bare bars with different load ranges, maintaining the ratio between the fatigue valley and peak loads constant. Applied loads higher than 40% of the bar tensile strength f_f are not representative of loads applied to GFRP-reinforced members under service condition, which are usually subjected to applied loads lower than $0.2f_f$ (D'Antino et al., 2022). Furthermore, tensile testing

of bare bars cannot provide information on the interaction between the bar and concrete under cyclic loading, which could affect the reinforced concrete (RC) member behavior (Zhao et al., 2022).

In this paper, the results of two GFRP-reinforced concrete slabs tested using a four-point bending configuration are presented and discussed. One slab was tested under quasi-static loading condition, while the other was subjected to fatigue loading and then tested under quasi-static loading condition up to failure. Digital image correlation (DIC) was employed to obtain the crack opening in the slab and, in turn, the bar-concrete relative displacement at one side of the crack, named global slip g in this paper. In addition, pull-out tests of specimens comprising the same bar and concrete were performed, investigating the influence of three different bar-concrete bonded lengths on the behavior observed. The bar applied load – global slip obtained from the slabs was compared with that of the pull-out tests, which showed that the pull-out test provides an upper bound estimation of the bar global slip observed in the slab.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material characterization

GFRP bars comprising E-glass and vinyl-ester resin were employed. The bar had a nominal diameter $d_b=12$ mm and a lugged (grooved) surface (Figure 1). The actual diameter declared by the manufacturer was 13.2 mm, which provided a cross-sectional area $A_{bar}=137$ mm² (Hudhayfah, 2021). The bar tensile strength and elastic modulus were 1155 MPa and 62.5 GPa, respectively, as declared by the manufacturer.

A normal-weight concrete with a maximum aggregate size of 13 mm was used to cast the slabs and pull-out specimens. The concrete mean compressive strength f'_c and mean splitting strength f'_t were determined at different concrete ages by compressive and splitting tests of three cylinders for each type of test and concrete age, as reported in Table 1.

Figure 1: GFRP bars studied

Table 1: Concrete mechanical properties at different ages

Property	Age [days] (CoV)		
	14	28	94
f'_c [MPa]	25.57 (0.049)	27.86 (0.013)	33.72 (0.046)
f'_t [MPa]	2.49 (0.171)	2.68 (0.227)	2.86 (0.030)

Pull-out specimens and set-up

Six pull-out specimens comprising a concrete cylinder with an embedded GFRP bar were tested. Three bonded lengths ℓ were considered, namely $5d_b=60$ mm (two specimens), $10d_b=120$ mm (three specimens), and $20d_b=240$ mm (one specimens). It should be noted that ASTM D7913 (ASTM International, 2020) and ISO 10406-1 (European Committee for Standardization, 2015) prescribe a bonded length equal to $5d_b$ and $4d_b$ for pull-out testing, respectively. In this study, different bonded lengths were considered to fully investigate the bar bond behavior. Specimens were cast with the GFRP bar centered in the concrete cylinder, leaving a 50 mm-long protruding part at the free end and a 140 mm-long bond breaker at the loaded end (Figure 2). Tests were carried out by constraining the concrete cylinder while pulling the bar. A steel pipe 305 mm-long was epoxy bonded to the bar end to facilitate gripping by the testing machine and avoid local bar failure. Three LVDTs attached to the bar

outside the bonded length at the loaded end were used to measure the bar-concrete relative displacement, i.e., the global slip g , defined as the average measurement of the three LVDTs minus the elastic elongation of the bar portion from the loaded end to the point where the LVDTs were attached. Details of the pull-out set-up and a photo of a specimen are shown in Figure 2. The quasi-static pull-out tests were conducted in displacement control by monotonically increasing the average displacement measured by the three LVDTs at a constant rate of 0.88 mm/min.

Figure 2: Set-up employed for the pull-out test

Slab and four-point bending set-up

Two GFRP-reinforced concrete slabs were tested. The slab had width 900 mm, depth 216 mm, and clear span 2100 mm. The longitudinal reinforcement comprised four GFRP bars with nominal diameter 12 mm spaced 229 mm on center. In addition, 14 GFRP bars spaced at 150 mm on center were placed transversally on top of the longitudinal bars to promote an even distribution of the load across the specimen width and prevent concrete cracks due to shrinkage and temperature variations (Matthys & Taerwe, 2000). The dimensions and reinforcement of the slab are representative of typical bridge decks, as indicated by the recommendation of the bar manufacturer (Owens Corning & E.L. Robinson Engineering, 2021).

The slabs were tested using a four-point bending configuration, with the applied load points at a distance of 1111 mm. The load was applied using two transversal I-section beams with a steel cylinder welded to the bottom flange. A spreader beam connected to a hydraulic jack with a spherical hinge was used to load the I-section beams (Figure 3). The vertical displacement of the slab was measured with two LVDTs that reacted off of the I-section beams and two LVDTs that reacted off of aluminum plates attached to the slab at the supports. The load point deflection δ_{LVDT} was obtained by subtracting the average displacement measured at the supports from the average displacement of the I-section beams. The slab quasi-static test was conducted in displacement control by monotonically increasing the hydraulic jack stroke at a constant rate of 0.50 mm/min.

Figure 3: Set-up employed for the 4-point bending test

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pull-out specimens

The pull-out specimens failed due to slippage of the bar with respect to the embedding concrete. At completion of the test, some specimens were broken open and showed that failure occurred due to concrete shear failure at the GFRP bar rib surface level, with damage of the ribs.

The pull-out specimens were named according to the notation UL-Y-P-N, where UL indicates non-coated (non-lacquered) bars, Y is the bonded length expressed as a multiple of d_b , P indicates the presence of a protruding portion of the bar at the specimen free end, and N is the specimen number. The specimen tested are listed in Table 2, where P^* is the peak load obtained and \bar{P}^* is the average peak load of nominally equal specimens.

Table 2: Results of quasi-static pull-out tests

Specimen	ℓ (mm)	Age of concrete when tested (days)	P^* [kN]	\bar{P}^* [kN] (CoV)
UL-5-P-1	60	106	32.73	34.13 (0.041)
UL-5-P-2	60	108	35.53	
UL-10-P-1	120	108	62.38	60.65 (0.042)
UL-10-P-2	120	109	56.98	
UL-10-P-3	120	109	62.58	
UL-20-P-1	240	110	101.96	101.96

Figure 4 shows the applied load P – global slip g responses of the pull-out tests. These responses showed an initial linear branch followed by a non-linear branch up to the attainment of the peak load. After P^* , the applied load decreased showing oscillations previously observed by the authors in pull-out tests of different GFRP bars (Zhao et al., 2022). Results of this paper confirms that the load oscillations in the softening portion of the load response are caused by the specific bar surface. Figure 4 shows that the peak load increased with increasing the bonded length. However, this increase was non-linear, as previously observed by the authors for different GFRP bars (Zhao et al., 2022).

Figure 4: Applied load – loaded end slip of pull-out tests

Slab specimens

The slabs were named S-W-L-N, where S=slab, W=slab width (in mm), L=slab clear span (in mm), and N is the specimen number. Slab S-900-2100-01 was tested under quasi-static loading condition, whereas slab S-900-2100-02 was subjected to fatigue loading. The valley and peak cyclic loads were 10 kN and 40 kN, respectively, while the cycle frequency was 1.5 Hz. The load range was determined based on cross-section analysis to match the fatigue load limit enforced in (ACI 440, 2015). After 500k cycles, the fatigue load was interrupted and the slab tested under quasi-static conditions up to an applied load of 100 kN, to simulate the application of the maximum service load. Then, the fatigue cycles were restarted and interrupted when 5 million cycles were attained. Finally, the slab was tested up to failure under quasi-static loading condition.

Both slab specimens failed in shear. The applied force F – load point deflection $\delta_{LVD T}$ obtained are provided in Figure 5 for each specimen. Figure 5 also shows some fatigue cycles associated to different times of the test, as well as a call-out of the initial part of the load responses. The $F - \delta_{LVD T}$ curves showed that the fatigue cycles did not significantly affect the behavior of the slab, which showed a consistent response for specimen S-900-2100-01 and S-900-2100-02. Indeed, the bending stiffness of the post-fatigue response of specimen S-900-2100-02 was similar to that obtained by specimen S-900-2100-01, which was not subjected to fatigue loading.

The force acting in the GFRP longitudinal bars P_{bar} during the quasi-static tests was computed by cross-sectional analysis. Concrete in compression was described by the parabola rectangle model (European Committee for Standardization, 2004), while concrete in tension by the linear-softening model proposed in (Kara & Ashour, 2012). This method allowed for computing P_{bar} for each value of the cross-section curvature (D’Antino et al., 2020). The bar global slip g was obtained by the DIC. Two squares with 8 mm size were selected on either side of a crack at the GFRP bar level. The average displacement of these two squares in the direction of the bar was computed. Assuming that the bar-concrete relative displacement was equal on either side of the crack, half of the difference between the average displacement of these two squares in the direction of the bar defined the bar global slip g . The P_{bar} - g responses associated with the crack that exhibited the largest opening as the bar load increased are shown in Figure 6 for each slab tested. In the same figure, these responses are compared with the P - g responses obtained by the pull-out tests. The comparison showed that the responses were similar only for low values of g . In fact, the pull-out specimens consistently showed a higher global slip for a given bar force than the slab specimens. Thus, global slips obtained by pull-out tests can be regarded as an upper bound estimation of the slips in GFRP reinforcing bars of concrete slabs.

Figure 5: Applied force – load point deflection of bending tests

Figure 6: Comparison between normalized load applied to the bar and corresponding slip obtained by pull-out and bending tests

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the results obtained by two GFRP-reinforced concrete slab four-point bending tests were presented. The GFRP bars had nominal diameter 12 mm and lugged surface. One slab was tested under quasi-static loading condition, whereas the other was subjected to 5 million cycles and then tested in quasi-static loading condition until failure. As expected, both slabs failed in shear. The fatigue loading did not significantly affect the slab behaviour, which showed a bending stiffness after fatigue cycles similar to that observed on the slab tested under quasi-static condition only.

Digital image correlation was employed to obtain the bar-concrete relative displacement, i.e., the bar global slip, which was combined with the result of cross-sectional analysis to determine the relationship between the bar force and global slip.

In addition, pull-out tests of the same GFRP bar and concrete comprising the slabs were performed. Three different bonded lengths were investigated, namely 5, 10, and 20 times the bar nominal diameter. The results showed a non-linear increase of the bar peak load with increasing the bonded length. All pull-out tests failed due to slippage of the bar with respect to the embedding concrete, with concrete shear failure at the bar level. The applied load – global slip responses of pull-out tests were compared with those computed by DIC and cross-sectional analysis of the slab, showing that the pull-out test provides a global slip that could be regarded as an upper bound estimation of the bar slip in GFRP-reinforced concrete slabs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was carried out in the framework of the DPC-ReLUIIS 2022–2024 project (WP 14) funded by the Italian Department of Civil Protection.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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